

ν (N-H) stretch and ν (C-O-C) stretch show -ve and +ve shift respectively with respect to free morpholine and indicate morpholine coordinates through nitrogen atom⁶. Similarly, the sharp bands at ~ 2940 and ~ 1040 cm^{-1} are attributed to the presence of N-coordinated α -pic⁷. The broad band at ~ 3400 cm^{-1} and sharp band at ~ 870 cm^{-1} in both the complexes indicates the presence of coordinated water molecule⁸.

Thermal decomposition: Thermal decomposition of morpholine complexes reveals no weight loss at 100° indicating that the water molecules are not in the lattice. The different products from the weight loss obtained by thermal decomposition are as follows:

where L = anion of dibasic acids.

In the light of the above evidences, it is suggested that all the complexes are five coordinated anionic complexes.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P. C. P.) is grateful to the management of Rourkela Steel Plant for kind help.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Cadmium(II) with Oxine as Primary Ligand and Heterocyclic and Aromatic Amines as Secondary Ligands

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Manuscript received 12 November 1981, revised 11 June 1982, accepted 21 July 1982

Oxine is known to possess both antifungal and antibacterial properties¹⁻³. It also behaves as an uninegative bidentate chelating ligand having ON potential donor sites. The present note describes the synthesis and characterisation of some

mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) and cadmium(II) with nitrogen donor heterocyclic and aromatic bases.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of metal oxinates: To an aqueous solution of metal chloride (2.36 g in case of cobaltous chloride and 2.01 g in case of cadmium chloride), sodium acetate (5 g) was added and warmed to $65-70^\circ$. The ethanolic solution of oxine (3.0 g) was added to it separately when light brown amorphous cobalt oxinate or light yellow amorphous cadmium oxinate separated out immediately. The metal oxinates thus formed were allowed to stand overnight and then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of mixed ligand complexes: To an ethanolic suspension of metal oxinate nitrogen donor ligands were added separately and refluxed for 1-2 hr. The compounds were then filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

The metal contents of the complexes were estimated by EDTA titration method and nitrogen by microanalytical method. Conductance of the complexes was measured in 10^{-3} M acetone solution using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes were recorded in 10^{-3} M DMF-base solution using Hilgerwatt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Analytical data of the complexes prepared are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation are of the type $[\text{ML}_2\text{L}'_2]$ and $[\text{ML}_2\text{L}']$ where M = cobalt(II), cadmium(II); LH = oxine; L' = pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, quinoline, piperidine, 2,6-lutidine, 4-aminopyridine, quinaldine, morpholine; L'' = *o*-phenylenediamine, 1,10-phenanthroline or 2-2'-bipyridine. The complexes show low conductance values in acetone medium (Δ_M ranges from 8.5 to 15 mhos cm^2) indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

IR spectra of the ligand, metal oxinate and mixed ligand complexes are informative. The ir active bands at 1500, 1280 and 900 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the phenolic OH deformation modes coupled with C-O stretching modes ($\nu_{\text{CO}} + \nu_{\text{OH}}$) and to the out of plane deformation vibration (σ_{OH}), respectively. The absence of these bands in the spectra of the metal oxinates indicates that the proton of the hydroxyl group is replaced by the metal ions. The bands at 1450, 1260, 1095 and 1060 cm^{-1} in the spectra of both heterocyclic ligands and mixed ligand complexes are characteristic of substituted pyridine ring vibration⁴. A medium broad band appears at ~ 3450 cm^{-1} region in case of metal oxinates assignable⁵ to $\nu(\text{O-H})$ of

TABLE I—ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Sl. No.	Compound	%Metal		μ_{eff} B.M.
		Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	
1.	CoI ₂ (Py) ₂	11.59 (11.66)	10.97 (11.09)	4.9
2.	CoL ₂ (β-Pic) ₂	11.00 (11.09)	10.48 (10.54)	5.1
3.	CoL ₂ (γ-Pic) ₂	10.97 (11.09)	10.52 (10.54)	4.9
4.	CoL ₂ (Q) ₂	9.68 (9.73)	9.20 (9.25)	4.9
5.	CoL ₂ (Pip) ₂	11.35 (11.39)	10.73 (10.83)	4.9
6.	CoL ₂ (2,6-Lut) ₂	10.48 (10.57)	10.02 (10.05)	5.0
7.	CoL ₂ (Quin) ₂	9.27 (9.30)	8.76 (8.84)	4.8
8.	CoL ₂ (4-AP) ₂	10.94 (11.01)	10.38 (10.48)	4.9
9.	CoL ₂ (Mor) ₂	11.26 (11.30)	10.63 (10.75)	4.9
10.	CoL ₂ ,o-PhDA	12.38 (12.94)	12.27 (12.31)	4.9
11.	CoL ₂ ,1,10-Phe	11.08 (11.17)	10.58 (10.62)	5.0
12.	CoL ₂ ,2-2'-bipy	11.68 (11.71)	11.10 (11.13)	5.0
13.	CdL ₂ (Py) ₂	19.95 (20.12)	9.97 (10.02)	—
14.	CdL ₂ (β-Pic) ₂	19.17 (19.23)	9.51 (9.58)	—
15.	CdL ₂ (γ-Pic) ₂	19.15 (19.23)	9.48 (9.58)	—
16.	CdL ₂ (Q) ₂	16.94 (17.07)	8.43 (8.50)	—
17.	CdL ₂ (2,6-Lut) ₂	18.28 (18.41)	9.12 (9.17)	—
18.	CdL ₂ (Pip) ₂	19.68 (19.70)	9.76 (9.81)	—
19.	CdL ₂ ,o-PhDA	22.04 (22.10)	10.97 (11.01)	—

Py = pyridine, β-Pic = β-picoline, γ-Pic = γ-picoline, Q = quinoline, Pip = piperidine, 2,6-Lut = 2,6-lutidine, Quin = quinaldine, 4-AP = 4-amino-pyridine, Mor = morpholine, o-PhDA = o-phenylenediamine, 1,10-Phe = 1,10-phenanthroline, 2-2'-bipy = 2-2'-bipyridine.

coordinated water molecules and its conspicuous absence in the mixed ligand complexes support the coordination of nitrogen donor ligands to the metal ions.

In the electronic spectra, the cobalt(II) complexes in DMF solution give rise to two absorption bands with maxima around 8.6 and 19.7 kK region which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) transitions. These absorption bands along with its magnetic moment values indicate a high-spin octahedral configuration for cobalt(II) complexes.

All the cadmium(II) complexes are six-coordinated on the basis of analysis, conductance and ir spectral studies.

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Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) with Schiff Base Derived from Bis-p(Aminophenyl) Sulphide and 2-Acetyl Thiophene Glyoxal

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Manuscript received 11 September 1980, revised 5 December 1981,
accepted 1 May 1982

IN continuation to our work¹⁻³ on Schiff base complexes, present note describes the preparation and characterisation of complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) with the Schiff base (I). Conductance, magnetic moment, electronic and infrared spectra of the complexes have been studied.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by taking the bis-p(aminophenyl) sulphide and 2-acetyl thiophene glyoxal in dioxane in equimolar quantities and refluxing for about 1 hr. The refluxed mass was poured into ice cold water when an orange coloured mass separated out. It was dried in a vacuum desiccator and recrystallised from ethanol. Bright orange coloured fine crystals, m.p. 186°, were obtained.

A general procedure was adopted to synthesise the complexes by mixing Co(II), Ni(II), Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) chloride (10 m mole each) in 25 ml acetone with 10 m mole of the ligand separately. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min and concentrated in a vacuum desiccator, yielding the coloured crystalline material. The crystals were washed with ether and dried.

The analysis of carbon, nitrogen and sulphur were done at the micro analytical section of C. D. R. I., Lucknow. The chloride was estimated by Volhard's method. The metal contents in all

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